

Optically active 4-formyl β -lactams: Microwave-induced deacetonation-oxidation

Ram Naresh Yadav^{a,b}, Indrani Banik^c and Bimal Krishna Banik^{b,c,d*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering & Technology, Veer Bahadur Singh Purvanchal University, Jaunpur-222 003, Uttar Pradesh

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Texas-Pan American, 1201 W. University Dr., Edinburg, TX 78539, USA

^cThe University of Texas M. D. Anderson Cancer Center, Department of Molecular Pathology, 1515 Holcombe Blvd, Houston, TX 77030, USA

^dCurrent Address: Community Health System of South Texas, 3135 South Sugar Road, Edinburg, TX 78539, USA

E-mail: bimalbanik10@gmail.com; bimal.banik@chsst.org

Manuscript received 03 October 2018, accepted 02 November 2018

Microwave-induced chiral synthesis of 4-formyl β -lactams is performed following a one-pot reaction. The deprotection of the ketal with aqueous bismuth nitrate and subsequent oxidation of the diol to aldehyde by aqueous sodium metaperiodate is accomplished to obtain the optically active 4-formyl β -lactams in good yield.

Keywords: β -Lactam, deprotection, oxidation, one-pot, microwave.

Introduction

Research on β -lactams is one of the most important areas¹. Many β -lactams are used as antibiotics². However, other clinical and pre-clinical applications of β -lactams are also well established³. Synthesis of optically active β -lactams with minimum number of steps and easy method are crucial because natural and non-natural products can be prepared from them⁴. In this paper, a simple and fast method for the preparation of chiral 4-formyl β -lactams is described through microwave-induced reactions⁵. In contrast to conventional method, microwave-assisted procedure is much more efficient in all respects. This method does not require any nitrogen atmosphere and dry conditions. The reaction is extremely rapid, the entire process is economical, work-up procedure is simple and all the reactions can be performed in Erlenmeyer flasks⁶. The optically active aldehydes synthesized by this method are important precursors for the synthesis of biologically active heterocyclic molecules of diverse interests.

Results and discussion

These chiral β -lactams as reported herein are important starting compounds and synthetic intermediate for the synthesis of diverse β -lactams and nitrogen containing natural

and non-natural products. An easy and rapid access of these products would certainly facilitate our and others research in this area of current investigation. Herein we wish to report a simple and facile route for the accesses of 4-formyl β -lactams in excellent yield via a one-pot microwave-induced reaction.

This methodology involves in one-pot bismuth nitrate catalyzed deacetonation followed by oxidation of vicinal diol with metaperiodate in aqueous condition.

The optically active β -lactam **1** on reaction with aqueous bismuth nitrate under microwave irradiation produced the intermediate vicinal diol which upon oxidation with aqueous sodium metaperiodate in THF produced the 4-formyl derivative **2** (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of β -lactam-4-carbaldehyde via metaperiodate cleavage of vic-diol.

Diverse compounds have been prepared through this process within a short reaction time and high yield (Table 1).

Table 1

Entry	1		2	2		Time (min)	Yield (%)
	R ¹	R ²		R ¹	R ²		
1a	Acetoxy	Phenyl	2a	Acetoxy	Phenyl	2	87
1b	Acetoxy	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	2b	Acetoxy	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	2	88
1c	Acetoxy	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	2c	Acetoxy	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	2	85
1d	Acetoxy	Benzyl	2d	Acetoxy	Benzyl	2	80
1e	Phenoxy	Phenyl	2e	Phenoxy	Phenyl	3	82
1f	<u>Phenoxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	2f	<u>Phenoxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	3	83
1g	<u>Phenoxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	2g	<u>Phenoxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	3	85
1h	<u>Phenoxy</u>	Benzyl	2h	<u>Phenoxy</u>	Benzyl	3	80
1i	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	Phenyl	2i	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	Phenyl	3	82
1j	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	2j	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	3	85
1k	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	2k	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	3	80
1l	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	Benzyl	2l	<u>Benzyloxy</u>	Benzyl	3	81

The mechanism of the ketal deprotection of **3** involves the protonation of the oxygen of the acetonide moiety and this process creates a positively charged oxonium ion **4**. In aqueous solution, bismuth nitrate can liberate nitric acid and thus it is capable of donating a proton to the electronegative oxygen of the acetonide moiety. The oxonium ion **4** breaks down spontaneously to a stabilized tertiary carbocation **5** which on immediate reaction with water generates **6**. Then one of the proton process creates **7** and finally it gives the diol **8** (Scheme 2). The liberated acid is unable to attack the carbonyl group of the β -lactam.

Scheme 2. Bismuth nitrate catalysed deacetonation of acetonide.

There was no cleavage of the β -lactam ring and no nitration of the aromatic groups present in the ring structures. Mechanistically the aldehyde **2** is formed from **1**. The diol **1** reacts with sodium metaperiodate and forms a complex. The complex on an intramolecular nucleophilic attack and subsequent cleavage reaction produces the aldehyde through **II** and **III** (Scheme 3). The deketalization and oxidation are facilitated substantially under microwave irradiation.

Scheme 3. General mechanistic pathway for the oxidation of vic-diol to carbaldehyde.

However, these reactions are performed in a small scale (100 mg to 500 mg). Because of the oxidizing properties of bismuth nitrate and sodium metaperiodate, it is important to exercise cautions when performing these reactions under rapid exposure to microwave.

It is important to note that under this condition there was no rupture of the C-N and N-C-O bonds of the β -lactams. In our earlier publications, the oxidizing power of bismuth salts is demonstrated. Particularly sodium bismuthate and trivalent bismuth compounds are oxidizing agents. Considering this oxidizing ability, it was assumed that bismuth nitrate under the reaction conditions would also oxidize the intermediate diol. The diol structure is ideal to form a coordination complex with trivalent bismuth cation and therefore, such an oxidation was possible. Since bismuth nitrate alone failed to oxidize the diol, sodium metaperiodate was used to accomplish the oxidation reaction. Clearly, bismuth nitrate under

the reaction conditions failed to nitrate the aromatic rings present in the β -lactams. It is also important to state that mild acid (*p*-toluene sulfonic acid) is able to form the diol under refluxing solution of benzene. Thus, by judiciously adjusting the reaction conditions and reagents, it is possible to perform numerous sensitive reactions on β -lactams for the preparation of important chiral compounds.

Experimental

A representative experimental procedure is given below.

β -Lactam **1** (1 mmol) was added to a solution of THF/water (1:1, 4 mL). To this bismuth nitrate pentahydrate (1 equivalent with respect to starting compound) was added and the mixture was irradiated in a microwave oven for 2–3 min maintaining the temperature of the reaction around 50°C. The progress of the reaction was followed by TLC. After the complete consumption of the starting material, sodium metaperiodate (2 equivalent) solution in water and THF was added to the reaction mixture and it was irradiated for 2–3 min. Dichloromethane (20 mL) was added to the reaction mixture and the contents were shaken thoroughly. The organic part was collected and washed with water (5 mL), dried with sodium sulfate and evaporated. The pure product **2** was obtained through a small column of silica gel (5 g) using ethyl acetate and hexane as the solvent (30: 70).

Conclusion

Optically active 4-formyl β -lactams with defined absolute stereochemistry is prepared by an expeditious route through microwave-induced reaction. Products are highly functionalized and therefore a number of chemical alterations are possible for the preparation of crucial molecules in optically active forms. The two reactions are performed in a single

Erlenmeyer flask with an aqueous THF solution. These results are extremely important because important compounds are prepared very rapidly through a non-expensive way. The products are so versatile that these can be used for the preparation of monocyclic to polycyclic β -lactams and numerous other heterocyclic compounds.

Acknowledgements

BKB gratefully acknowledges the financial support from US National Institute of Health and US National Cancer Institute.

References

1. G. N. Robinson, *J. Antimicrobial. Chemo.*, 1998, **41**, 589.
2. Kok-Fai Kong, Lisa Schneper and Kalai Mathee, *APIMS*, 2010, **118**, 1.
3. William A. Craig, *Infect. Dis. Clin. N. Am.*, 2003, **17**, 479.
4. (a) H. Lu and C. Li, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 5365; (b) C. J. Abraham, D. H. Paull, C. Dogo-Isonagie and T. Lectka, *Synlett*, 2009, 1651; (c) E. C. Lee, B. L. Hodous, E. Bergin, C. Shih and G. C. Fu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 11586; (d) M. R. Linder and J. Podlech, *Org. Lett.*, 2001, **3**, 1849; (e) M. Zarei and A. Jarrahpour, *Synlett*, 2011, 2572; (f) I. Banik, F. F. Becker and B. K. Banik, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2003, **46**, 12; (g) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2005, **13**, 3611; (h) B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 846; (i) B. K. Banik, S. Samajdar and F. F. Becker, *Mol. Med. Rep.*, 2010, **3**, 319; (j) A. L. Shaikh, O. Esparza and B. K. Banik, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2011, **94**, 2188.
5. (a) A. K. Bose, B. K. Banik and M. S. Manhas, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, **36**, 213; (b) D. Bandyopadhyay and B. K. Banik, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **93**, 298; (c) I. Banik, S. Samajdar and B. K. Banik, *Heterocyclic Letters*, 2011, 55; (d) D. Bandyopadhyay, M. Yanez and B. K. Banik, *Heterocyclic Letters*, 2011, 65.
6. Arumugam Sudalai, Alexander Khenkin and Ronny Neumann, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2015, **13**, 4374.

